

UNCERTAINTIES IN THE PREDICTION OF CFRP LAMINATE PROPERTIES IN THE CONTEXT OF A RELIABILITY BASED DESIGN APPROACH

C. Schillo^{1*}, D. Krause¹

¹ Institute of Product Development and Mechanical Engineering Design, Hamburg University of Technology, Germany

* conny.schillo@tuhh.de

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Abstract

In order to pursue a reliability based design approach, material related uncertainties need to be quantified. For composite structural designers, the evaluation starts at the coupon level where a limited number of layups gets tested. The state of the art stiffness determination process then neglects the non-linear stiffness behavior as well as the spatial variability and aims at conservative estimates. In the present work, a unidirectional laminate is tested in tension and the stiffness is evaluated at different loading points. Monte Carlo simulation technique is used to predict laminate stiffnesses based on this data for two different layups and compared to a similar simulation based on constituent properties. The predictive qualities are checked against measured laminate stiffnesses.

Furthermore, polynomial curve fits are generated for each specimen and mean and confidence intervals evaluated for a strain working range of interest and compared to the secant method suggested by the respective Norm. A simple beam problem is used to illustrate the consequences of the different stiffness determination methods.

In the considered tension case the maximum computed deviation of a specific stress quantile to the reference stress quantile is around 5%. The evaluation methods investigated lead to significantly higher deviations when comparing the respective deflections, thus suggesting that ultimately a more robust testing and evaluation method needs to be applied. This is especially true since in case of stiffness determined designs the usage of a low estimate of the stiffness is not necessarily a conservative assumption.

1 Motivation for reliability based design

In the structural design process it is common practice to consider only nominal means as input

variables and evaluate the one resulting design against the design criteria. To guarantee a certain degree of conservatism, the actual stress is not compared to the material strength but to the material strength times an empirically based safety factor. Although this approach can usually be called successful in terms of low failure rates and implicit conservatism, the neglect of variant input data leads to several shortcomings. Firstly, to guarantee a conservative design, the deterministic approach requires assuming a worst case scenario for all input parameters and all occurring simultaneously, thus leading to overly conservative and heavy designs. Secondly, the system inherent safety is in fact often not known. Especially for the development of prototypes, the application of safety factors can be subject to discussions. A commonly asked question is then how far the safety factor can be reduced in favour of the goals lightweight design and low cost. Since there is generally not enough information about relevant scatter of input variables and their influence on the structural behavior, the safety factor cannot easily be changed. To exploit lightweight potential, it is hence necessary to quantify relevant uncertainties of influencing parameters and the structural sensitivity towards them. This is also the basis to apply a reliability based design approach. To implement such an approach in the design process, the material and structural properties as well as their scatter in situ need to be known. But although there is a large number of work related to uncertainty modeling techniques, only few data regarding quantitative characterization of FRP-structural related uncertainties is available [1].

2 Determinations of Material Properties

Commonly, material properties are measured in coupon tests and the resulting stiffness and strength data is used for the structural design of the

component. For structures made of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP), the representation of laminate properties in situ through coupons is not equally straightforward. In contrast to metal structures, where material that has already been made is used for the structure and the coupons, the FRP is made together with the structure and can differ in its manufacturing process from the coupon.

Furthermore, the hierarchical structure of fiber composites leads to uncertainties on different scales of the structural behavior [2]. Theoretically, uncertainties on a lower scale are present on higher scales. But in structural design, usually the lowest scale considered is the ply or coupon level. On this level material properties are measured, rather than measuring fiber and matrix properties separately. Considering a multiscale approach from the ply level on, one now has to consider that uncertainties on coupon level are not necessarily the same as on component level.

On the coupon level it is well known that property measurements are strongly related to the testing method [3], the preparation of the probe [6], [4] layup [4], [5] and edge treatment. For example, this sensitivity is among others due to arising edge effects, which generally are not or not that distinct present in the structural component. On the structural scale, the component is more prone to manufacturing related uncertainties like complexity of the structure, contours or type of process [7].

3 Analyses

3.1 Material and specimens

The carbon fiber reinforced polymer investigated is a prepreg system consisting of 24k intermediate strength carbon fibers (IMS65) and epoxy matrix. The unidirectional sheets have a nominal thickness of 0.125 mm and are delivered on a roll with a width of 300 mm. Three different lay-ups are prepared for the analysis: unidirectional (UD) $[0^8]_s$, crossply (CP) $[90/0/90/0]_s$ and quasi-isotropic (QI) $[90/45/0/-45]_s$. For all laminates two plates are made using hand lay-up technique. After preparing four layers, a vacuum is applied to avoid air captures between layers. The curing cycle is run in an autoclave following a cycle proposed by the manufacturer with a maximum temperature of 130°C hold for 90 minutes. After cooling and application of gfrp and aluminium strips in a hot press (60°C) for

clamping purposes, seven to nine specimens are cut from the produced plates. The final edge treatment is done using abrasive paper with a grain size of P1000. A typical sample is depicted in Fig.1.

Figure 1 Specimen dimensions

The characterization of the material is achieved by conducting tension tests according to DIN EN ISO 527 with a Zwick universal testing machine 1474. The test speed is kept constant at 2 mm/min to ensure quasi-static behavior.

Strains are measured using a Zwick/Roell extensometer 6336.102b, whereby some samples had additional strain gauges to verify the extensometer results (Fig.2).

Figure 2 Tension test with extensometer

A normal distribution is assumed for the distribution of the longitudinal stiffness E_x :

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

The first central moment or mean value of the actually discrete distribution is

$$\mu_x = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (2)$$

The standard deviation results from the evaluation of the second central moment, the variance σ^2

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - \mu_x)^2 \quad (3)$$

An additional measure for the scatter of the data is the coefficient of variation, which is defined as

$$V_X = \frac{\sigma_X}{\mu_X} \quad (4)$$

3.2 Analytical approach

Micro-meso analysis

Based on the assumptions for the constituent properties, the engineering constants are computed deterministically and used as reference values for the discussion of the tension test results.

A Monte Carlo simulation is conducted to compute the expected mean and standard deviation for the engineering constant E_x of the tested laminates. This prediction is considered as a micro-meso approach, since data from the constituent (or micro) level are used to predict properties on the laminate or meso level. The data used as random input for this simulation is summarized in Tab.1.

	μ	source	V	source
Ef1	290 GPa	data sheet	4.5 %	assumption
Ef2	23.2 GPa	ESAComp	4.5 %	assumption
fV	52 %	measured	0.8 %	measured
E_M	3.5 GPa	assumption	3 %	[8]
Deg	0°	-	2°	[9]

Table 1 Constituent input data

The layer thickness has not been considered separately as varying parameter since it is not independent from the fiber volume fraction: the number of fibers within the layer does not vary, so measured thickness variations are related to fluctuations in matrix content. Poisson ratios of the constituents have been identified to only minor contribute to the results in a sensitivity analysis and are not further considered as varying parameters either.

Layer parameters are computed using common rules of mixture for E_1 :

$$E_1 = fV \cdot E_{f1} + (1-fV) \cdot E_m \quad (5)$$

Transverse stiffness E_2 is calculate using a modification in accordance with Puck

$$E_2 = \frac{E_m}{1-v_m^2} \cdot \frac{1+0.85 \cdot fV^2}{(1-fV)^{1.25} + \frac{fV((E_m/(1-v_m^2)))}{E_{f2}}} \quad (6)$$

The shear modulus of the single layer is calculated using

$$G_{12} = \frac{1}{\frac{fV}{G_{f12}} + \frac{1-fV}{G_m}} \quad (7)$$

Applying the classical laminate theory (CLT) the engineering constants for the desired lay-up are computed. The resulting stiffnesses are used as reference values.

Meso-meso analysis, secant method

In the next step a meso-meso approach is carried out, characterized by the usage of E_1 stiffness values of the UD specimens evaluated between different strain levels. Effectively, a secant is computed between a defined lower and upper value on the stress strain curve and the gradient is evaluated as the respective stiffness (Fig.3).

Figure 3 Examples of secants at stress-strain curve

Based on CLT, these values are used for the predictions of laminate properties of a CP- and QI-laminate. For each laminate type a Monte Carlo simulation is carried out using the measured mean and standard deviation of the respective measured stiffness values. Hence, for each evaluated strain level a separate analysis is carried out per laminate. Transverse stiffness E_2 and shear modulus G_{12} are measured according to DIN 65378 and DIN 65466 respectively

	μ [GPa]	V [%]
E_2	6.8	3.4
G_{12}	3.0	7.0

Table 2 Measured transverse and shear modulus Meso-meso analysis, curve fitting method

For each specimen tested, a curve fitting is applied for the stress-strain curve. Due to the limited practical relevant working strain range, the curves are established between 0.15 % and 0.35 % strain only. Among other reasons, this is also based on the fact that at slightly higher strain levels micro-damages in the matrix or fiber-matrix interfaces of transversely oriented layers already occur. Since transversely oriented layers play an important role in practical applications, this working range can be found in different kind of industries [10],[11].

The curves are described by fourth grade polynomial functions which are established by computing regression curves based on the least square method. In the next step first derivatives are formed for each resulting function. The resulting set of curves describing a smoothed stiffness behavior are analyzed at certain evaluation points. At these points mean values and 95 % confidence intervals for the mean are computed. Those finally result in a respective mean value curve as well as upper and lower bound for a confidence interval. While this assessment describes the expected range for the mean value, the analyzed 4σ interval represents the range in which 95.4 % of all specimens will fall.

3.2 Influence on structural assessment

The different stiffness evaluation methods lead to different predictions and possibly diverging decisions in the design process.

For illustrational purposes, a simple beam model is used with varying resulting engineering constants depending on the evaluation method used. A Matlab code is set up and the respective Monte Carlo simulation uses 6000 runs per analysis. The beam has a width of 50 mm, is clamped at one edge and loaded in bending through a point load at the other edge (Fig.3).

Figure 4 Simple beam problem

The engineering constants of the beam are computed using CLT. A layerwise stress analysis is performed and the maximum stress at the tension side is evaluated. The maximum deflection is computed according to classical beam theory assuming pure bending and neglecting possible shear effects. Each Monte Carlo simulation results in certain mean, standard deviation and confidence intervals for the observed quantity. Output that is compared is the 95 % upper confidence bound on the 4σ -quantile.

4. Results

4.1 Tension test specimens – secant method

According to DIN EN ISO 527 the Young's modulus E_x is evaluated by calculating the secant gradient between 0.05% and 0.25% strain. In this work, the young's modulus is evaluated for seven more strain ranges. Analyzing all specimen results, for each range, mean value and standard deviation can be computed. The procedure is repeated for the CP- and QI-laminate but with less data points. Fewer points are evaluated since for a number of specimens local damages occur below the final breakage which can distort the computation of the secant value at these ranges.

Fig. 5 shows the results for the UD specimens. For the first evaluation point between 0.05% and 0.25% strain the mean value lies significantly below the expected stiffness. In the working range mean values are around the expected value and increasing towards higher strains up to a mean of 159 GPa for

the highest evaluated range between 1.3 % and 1.4 % strain. The expected stiffness of 149 GPa gets exceeded not before a strain level of approximately 1 %.

The CP-laminate also shows differences in the stiffness according to DIN and compared to higher strain evaluation points. A mean of 81.2 GPa as predicted by rules of mixture is reached at the evaluation range between 1.1 % and 1.2 % strain. The tendency to exceed the expected stiffness value with increasing strain level is not as pronounced as observed for the UD-specimens.

Figure 5 Stiffness evaluation of UD-laminate

Figure 6 Stiffness evaluation of CP-laminate

Fig.7 depicts the tension test results of the Quasi-isotropic laminates. Above 1 % strain no more strain ranges were evaluated due to slipping effects of the extensometer that occurred and distorted the secant

analysis. The mean of the tension tests are 10 % to 20 % below the expected mean but show no tendency to increase with respect to the strain level.

Figure 7 Stiffness evaluation of QI-laminate

4.2 Tension test specimens – curve fit method

The evaluation of first derivatives of the fourth grade polynomial fitting functions leads to Fig.8. The UD stiffness in the analyzed range shows a strong increasing tendency from 132 GPa at 0.15 % strain to about 140 GPa at 0.35 % strain. Depicted in grey is the 4σ -intervall which includes 95.4 % of the sample data points.

While the variance of the UD stiffness stay approximately constant at 2.5% over the considered range, variance of CP- and QI longitudinal stiffnesses show a tendency to decrease by up to 1 % within the 0.2 % strain range (Fig. 9, Fig. 10 and Tab. 3).

Figure 8 Curve fit for UD-specimens

Figure 9 Curve fit for CP-specimens

Figure 10 Curve fit for QI specimens

Evaluation point	0.20 %	0.25 %	0.30 %
	V [%]	V [%]	V [%]
UD	2.4	2.5	2.5
CP	3.8	3.0	2.7
QI	3.3	2.9	2.3

Table 3 Curve fit – resulting variances

4.2 Analytical stiffness predictions

Fig. 11 to Fig. 13 depict the cumulative distribution functions of the different laminates investigated and show the specimen results as stairs and the analytical predictions made through Monte Carlo simulations as continuous curves.

For the UD material the Monte Carlo simulation based on constituent properties predicts a coefficient of variance of 2.18 %, which is approximately 1-3 %

below measured variances (Fig.11). The prediction made coincides best with stiffness values analyzed at higher strains.

Figure 11 CDFs for UD-laminate

The various specimen results for mean and variances lead to different predictions for the CP- and QI-laminate cumulative distribution functions. In Fig.12 and Fig.13 they can be compared to the respective specimen results. Corresponding strain ranges used as input for the Monte Carlo simulation and evaluated for the respective laminate are depicted using a similar line style.

Although the predicted variances are comparable, the corresponding means experience partly significant offsets. Especially for the QI-specimens, the predictions based on measured UD-stiffnesses considerably overestimate the longitudinal stiffness.

Figure 12 CDFs for CP-laminate

Figure 13 CDFs for QI-laminate

4.3 Beam problem

For the beam analysis the maximum stress occurring in a layer of the beam is evaluated as well as the maximum deflection. While the first value represents the stress peak within one layer, the deflection characterizes the overall laminate response.

The 95 % 4σ - quantiles for the beam analysis are summarized in Tab. 4. Results based on the stiffness values according to norm are chosen as reference values. The second column shows the deviation with respect to the reference.

Depending on the chosen approach to evaluate stiffness E_1 from specimen data, the analyzed quantile for the maximum stress shifts by up to 4.4 % for the UD-laminate. Deviations for the QI-laminate are slightly higher than for the CP-laminate and shift by a maximum of 5 %.

The deflection is more sensitive to the overall stiffness change investigated and shows significant shift with respect to the reference, as well as among each other. Stiffness input evaluated at the highest strain range leads to observations between 14 % (QI) and around 17 % (UD and CP) smaller than the reference.

Observations for the maximum stress made by using the curve fit method in the working range lead to smaller shifts. For all laminates the predicted shift is almost constant (between -2.3 to -2.7 % for the UD-laminate and less for CP- and QI-laminate).

Regarding deflection values, shifts are more pronounced and vary between around 4 %-7 % for UD- and CP-laminate and 2.6 - 4.2 % for the QI-laminate.

5. Discussion

The evaluation of the secant gradient is related to several uncertainties that can have significant influence on the absolute stiffness value. At low strains the low stiffness values found may be influenced by fiber waviness and stretching effects. Additionally, setting effects of the clamping material may occur due to increasing transverse forces. It is not expected that these sources take effect over the whole strain range.

Comparing Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 it can be observed that the predictions at corresponding strain levels do not consequently coincide with the evaluated CP-stiffnesses, thus indicating that the variations are not due to inherent material uncertainties. The same applies for the prediction of variances and data scatter, respectively.

		UD				CP				QI			
evaluation range [%]		σ [MPa]	deviation [%]	w [mm]	deviation [%]	σ [MPa]	deviation [%]	w [mm]	deviation [%]	σ [MPa]	deviation [%]	w [mm]	deviation [%]
secant method	0.05-0.25 (Reference)	296.2	-	12.3	-	577.3	-	36.0	-	688.5	-	56.6	-
	0.2-0.3	309.2	4.39	11.3	-7.90	600.5	4.02	34.0	-5.64	722.9	4.99	52.5	-7.18
	0.3-0.4	298.8	0.85	11.4	-7.01	582.7	0.94	33.8	-6.15	704.1	2.27	53.4	-5.63
	0.5-0.6	296.6	0.11	11.1	-9.68	582.6	0.92	32.9	-8.57	707.8	2.81	52.3	-7.62
	0.7-0.8	308.4	4.12	11.4	-7.37	597.9	3.57	34.1	-5.13	721.6	4.81	52.8	-6.73
	0.9-1.0	292.0	-1.42	10.1	-17.86	577.5	0.03	29.9	-16.89	716.7	4.10	48.8	-13.71
curve fit	0.2	288.1	-2.74	11.7	-4.65	567.0	-1.78	34.1	-5.24	685.9	-0.38	55.1	-2.61
	0.25	289.1	-2.40	11.5	-6.28	567.9	-1.63	33.8	-6.07	689.2	0.10	54.7	-3.32
	0.3	289.3	-2.34	11.4	-7.10	568.6	-1.51	33.4	-7.19	692.7	0.61	54.2	-4.20

Table 4 Beam analysis: 95 % - 4σ - quantiles and comparison for maxim stress s and end deflection w

Hence it is concluded, that other effects related to the evaluation and testing method might contribute to the high divergence between expected and evaluated stiffness values.

Although the evaluation at higher strain levels leads to increasing and thereby better matching stiffness values, a focus has been set on a working range of practical relevance. Here, both the secant and curve fitting method lead to values significantly below the ones expected by the classical laminate theory. The curve fitting method is effectively smoothing the resulting stress-strain curve and thus ruling out possible local discontinuities. Such discontinuities may for example be produced by the extensometer measuring or by local degradation effects like fiber-matrix debonding or micro damages within the matrix in the case of off-axis layers. Such degradation effects may lead to the observed reduction in stiffness of the QI-laminate, where off-axis layers ($\pm 45^\circ$) contribute more to the overall longitudinal stiffness compared to the off-axis layers of the CP-laminate (90°).

These effects clearly have an influence when trying to generate input data for a reliability based design case study. In case of the beam analysis, the effect is clearly visible in case of stress analysis and highly significant for the stiffness dominated deflection analysis. Principally, it seems acceptable to reduce the area of interest to a practical working range. The curve fitting method is less prone to local discontinuities of the stress-strain curve and leads to more consistent variances. Nonetheless, the fact remains that the specimens investigated did not show the expected stiffness behavior as predicted by CLT. Moreover, the usage of the (lower than expected) UD-specimen data did not lead to the prediction of CP- and QI-data, making it more than difficult to analyze what mean and variances of the material investigated truly are.

6. Conclusion

For the Prepreg system investigated, a significant apparent stiffness dependence on the strain level for Unidirectional specimens was found. At low strain levels the stiffness can lay 14 % below the expected value calculated through rules of mixture. For crossply and quasi-isotropic layups the effect is also present, while they are less prone to evaluation ranges. A curve fitting method specifically for the working range is proposed in order to smooth out

possible local distortions in the stress strain curve that might affect the evaluation through the secant method, thus leading to more consistent input data.

Due to the high dependence on the evaluation method it is concluded that the described specimens and the stiffness evaluation according to the respective norm do not lead to the real material inherent uncertainties needed for a reliability based design approach.

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